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College Students Physical Exercise And Emotional Management

Yanwen Lu *

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The present study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between physical activity behaviors and affective control among college students. The study adopted a quantitative research design. In order to obtain a representative sample, the study will use a stratified random sampling method to select a certain number of respondents from students of different grade levels. The sample included a total of 386 college students from the College. By investigating the basic profiles of the student respondents in terms of gender, age, grade level, and college affiliation, as well as their behaviors in terms of frequency, intensity, duration, and type of physical activity, the associations between these factors and the level of affective control were examined. The study also assessed students' performance in terms of emotional intensity, emotional stability, emotional expression, and emotional regulation strategies and explored possible associations between these aspects and physical activity behavior. In the mental health support and counseling services for university students, special attention should be paid to the emotional expression of students of different age groups, and corresponding mental health education and support should be provided. It is recommended that relevant policies and programs should be formulated to encourage all university students to participate in physical exercise in order to promote the health and vitality of the whole campus. It is recommended that the ability to control emotions should be incorporated into students' comprehensive quality development programs, so as to enhance students' confidence in their own learning and life.

Keywords: *university students, physical activity, emotional control, health promotion, mental health, overall development*

Introduction

Physical activity plays an important role in the lives of college students. In addition to providing opportunities for physical fitness, there is a strong relationship between physical education and academic performance and emotional management. In recent years, physical activity and emotional management among college students have received increasing research attention, as both aspects are critical to their overall development and academic success.

Physical activity has a prominent place on college campuses. It not only helps maintain students' physical health, but also provides socialization opportunities and emotional support networks. However, college students face a variety of challenges from academic pressures, social pressures, and personal growth and development (Wang, 2020). In this context, emotion management becomes a crucial factor as it directly affects students' mental health and academic performance.

Emotion management involves how individuals perceive, express, and regulate their emotions. College students face emotional challenges such as anxiety, stress, and depression in a variety of areas such as classroom pressures, social problems, and family relationships. The development of emotion management skills can help them better cope with these challenges and improve their mental health (Hai, 2018). However, the relationship between emotion management and physical activity is not fully understood.

College students vary in their level of participation in physical activity (Chen,2020). Some students are actively involved in physical activity, while others are less involved or do not participate. Physical activity is thought to improve physical health, but whether it is also associated with academic performance has yet to be studied. Researchers need to gain a deeper understanding of the interactions between physical activity and emotion management and how they affect college students' academic performance. Within this context, the main question of this study is: How do physical activity and emotion management affect college students' academic performance in physical education? Researchers will explore this question and seek to provide valuable insights in this critical area.

The timeliness of this study is well documented as university education and student health concerns continue to grow. Understanding how emotion management and physical activity affect the academic performance of college students will contribute to the development of more effective educational policies and the promotion of holistic student development. In this study, the researcher will use quantitative research methods to collect and analyze data to answer the research questions. By delving into the relationship between emotional control and academic performance in physical education, it is hoped that useful insights will be provided for the education and mental health of college students. This study focused on the relationship between physical activity, emotional control, and academic performance in physical education among college students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study will utilize a quantitative research design designed to explore the relationship between physical activity and affective

management among college students. In order to obtain a representative sample, the study will use a stratified random sampling method to select a certain number of respondents from students of different grades. In order to measure the variables of physical activity and emotional management. Physical activity levels will be assessed using self-report scales of frequency, intensity, duration, and type. Respondents will be asked to assess their level of emotional management using self-report scales of emotional intensity, emotional stability, emotional expression, and emotional regulation strategies.

The respondents of the study are the college students. In order to obtain a representative sample, the study will use a stratified random sampling method to select a certain number of respondents from students of different grades. In order to measure the variables of physical activity and emotional management. Physical activity levels will be assessed using self-report scales of frequency, intensity, duration, and type. Respondents will be asked to assess their level of emotional management using self-report scales of emotional intensity, emotional stability, emotional expression, and emotional regulation strategies.

The study will use statistical software to analyze the data in order to explore the relationship between physical activity and emotional management. First, the researcher will perform descriptive statistical analysis, including means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions to understand the basic characteristics of the sample and the distribution of the variables. Next, correlation analysis will be used to explore the relationship between the variables. In particular, correlations between physical activity variables and emotion management variables will be examined.

Quantitative research design, which can provide a quick overview of the relationship between different variables. Although causality cannot be established, this design can provide important initial insights for subsequent in-depth research. Through the use of self-report scales, researchers can obtain subjective feedback from respondents, which can help to understand their individual experiences with physical activity and emotional management. Ultimately, the results of the study will provide useful information about the holistic development and academic success of college students that will help improve educational practices and policies.

Respondents

The population of the study is the entire undergraduate population of Jiaying College and Guangzhou Xinhua College, totaling 10,143 students. This population consists of students in different grades, categorized into four grades: Freshman, Sophomore, Junior, and Senior.

This study will utilize a stratified sampling technique to ensure that the sample is representative of college students at different grade levels. First, the population will be divided into four grades, freshman, sophomore, junior, and senior. Each grade level is considered a sampling stratum. The sample size for each sampling stratum was determined based on the population size of each grade level. Within each sampling stratum, a sample will be randomly selected from the list of students in that grade level using computer-generated random numbers or a similar method. The sample size will take into account a 95% confidence interval, a 5% margin of error, and a final sample of 386 students will be identified for the study. The selected students will be informed of the purpose and procedures of the study and invited to participate in the study. The study will emphasize that their participation is voluntary, and they are free to choose whether or not to participate.

Table 1. *Sample Size Distribution*

<i>Grade</i>	<i>Total number of registered students</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Sample</i>
Freshman	2588	25.39	98
Sophomore	2690	26.68	103
Junior	2420	23.83	92
Senior	2445	24.10	93
Total	10143	100	386

Instruments

This study will use a self-edited questionnaire as the main data collection tool to study the required data and information.

The questionnaire consists of three parts, the first part involves the information of gender, age and grade of the respondents. The second part is the Physical Activity Scale, To measure the physical activity habits of college students, the researchers used a home-made questionnaire based on the FITTE principle (Frequency, Intensity, Time, Type) to collect data. The questionnaire included questions about frequency of exercise, intensity of exercise, time of exercise, and type of exercise. Each dimension consists of five entries, and these questions were designed based on relevant literature and expertise in the field of kinesiology to ensure that key aspects of physical activity are captured effectively. The third section was the Emotional Control Scale, which consists of four dimensions, namely, emotional intensity, emotional stability, emotional expression, and emotion regulation strategies. Each dimension includes five entries.

During the questionnaire design phase, experts in the field of kinesiology were consulted to ensure that the content of the questions effectively reflected the key variables of the study. The expert review helped to validate the content validity of the questionnaire to

ensure that the questions were measuring the concepts to be studied.

In order to assess the reliability of the questionnaire, an internal consistency test will be conducted. Specifically, the researcher used Cronbach's alpha coefficient to measure the internal consistency of the dimensions of the questionnaire. This helps to determine whether the questions in the questionnaire are highly consistent under the same dimension. The emotion regulation scale used in this study demonstrated good internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.87$).

Pre-testing of the questionnaire will be conducted prior to formal data collection. This involves testing the questionnaire on a group of 30 student respondents to check for clarity, comprehensibility of the questions and feedback from the respondents. Based on the results of the pre-testing, the researcher made some fine-tuning of the questionnaire to ensure its validity and credibility for formal data collection.

Results and Discussion

The Assessment of Student-Respondents Execute their Physical Exercises based on the FITT Principle

Table 2. Summary Table on the student-respondents execute their physical exercises

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
Frequency	2.56	.657	Agree	Good
Intensity	2.64	.528	Agree	Good
Time	2.55	.619	Agree	Good
Type	2.75	.608	Agree	Good
Overall Mean	2.62	.494	Agree	Good

N=386. Parameter limits: 3.51-4.00 Strongly agree/Excellent; 2.51-3.50 Agree/Good; 1.51-2.50 Disagree/Fair; 1.00-1.50 Strongly disagree/Poor

Table 2 summarizes students' overall ratings of frequency, intensity, time and type of physical activity performed. The mean values of the indicators were 2.56 (Frequency), 2.64 (Intensity), 2.55 (Time), and 2.75 (Type), with an overall mean of 2.62. These values were around 2 (Agree), indicating that the students as a whole had a positive attitude towards the execution of physical activity. The standard deviation of each indicator is 0.657 (Frequency), 0.528 (Intensity), 0.619 (Time), 0.608 (Type), and the overall standard deviation is 0.494. The small standard deviation indicates that the students' execution of physical activity has some consistency on the whole.

The highest scoring indicator was Type (type of physical activity) with a mean of 2.75. This indicates that students hold relatively high positive attitudes towards different types of physical activity. The lowest scoring indicator was Time with a mean of 2.55, although the score was lower, it was still around 2 (Agree), indicating that students still have positive attitudes towards scheduling physical activity. The overall mean score of 2.62 indicates that students' overall attitude towards physical activity is 'Agree'. This further emphasizes the students' positive identification with physical activity.

The results in Table 6 indicate that students generally showed positive attitudes towards the frequency, intensity, duration and type of physical activity performed, which is consistent with the findings of Yan (2019). Frequency, intensity, duration and type are the key factors that influence the effectiveness of physical activity and students' positive agreement with these factors positively affects their overall health and academic performance.

In terms of frequency, Zhang (2023) study noted that there is a positive association between regular participation in physical activity and cardiovascular health, physical health and mental health. Frequent physical activity helps to improve students' psychological state, improve learning outcomes, and enhance academic achievement. Past studies have also highlighted the positive impact of regular exercise on mood management, helping to alleviate academic stress and anxiety.

In terms of intensity, moderate physical activity has been shown to have a positive impact on students' cognitive functioning and academic performance. Moderate physical activity improves attention, memory, and motivation to learn, which helps to better cope with academic challenges (Wang, 2018). In addition, moderate intensity can help maintain physical health and provide students with better learning conditions.

In terms of time, Zhang and Zhao (2023). The study shows that reasonable time allocation for physical exercise is closely related to students' academic performance. Appropriate exercise time can improve students' learning efficiency and promote physical and psychological balance. However, excessive exercise time negatively affects academics, emphasizing the importance of moderation and sensible time management.

In terms of type, different types of physical exercise have different effects on students' physical and mental health. Aerobic exercise was found to be beneficial for cognitive functioning and academic performance, while strength training was associated with physical fitness and academic performance (Zhu, 2020). Ball sports and speed sports help improve coordination and teamwork, which positively affects students' social skills and academic achievement. Positive effects of physical activity on students' overall health and academic achievement. This provides support for further research on the relationship between physical activity and emotional management and academic achievement.

The Assessment of the Level of Emotional Control of the Student-Respondents

Table 3. Summary Table on the level of emotional control of the student – respondents

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
Emotional intensity	2.57	.562	Agree	Good
Emotional Stability	2.47	.595	Agree	Good
Emotional expression	2.64	.545	Agree	Good
Emotion regulation strategies	2.73	.536	Agree	Good
Overall Mean	2.60	.494	Agree	Good

N=386. Parameter limits: 3.51-4.00 Strongly agree/Excellent; 2.51-3.50 Agree/Good; 1.51-2.50 Disagree/Fair; 1.00-1.50 Strongly disagree/Poor

Table 3 summarizes the results of the student participants' assessment of the dimensions of emotional control. In terms of means, the scores for each dimension ranged from 2.47 to 2.73, and the standard deviations ranged from 0.494 to 0.595. This suggests that students' self-assessment of their level of emotional control shows some consistency overall, and that there is not a great deal of variation between the dimensions. The range of the means was between 2.47 and 2.73, which indicates that students tended to view their level of emotional control positively overall. The overall mean value of 2.60 falls into the "Agree" category, indicating that students have an overall positive view of their level of emotional control. This suggests that students perceive themselves to be good at dealing with their emotions and that they are able to strike a good balance between perceiving, expressing and regulating their emotions.

He (2021) showed that emotional control plays a key role in an individual's psychological well-being and social interactions, and Zhang and Li (2023) showed that moderate emotional intensity is positively associated with psychological well-being, and that students' performance in this area contributes to the promotion of positive affective experiences and better psychological resilience. Emotional stability is associated with psychological stability and adaptability, and Jiang and Chen (2019) noted that being able to effectively cope with changes in life contributes to the maintenance of good mental health. Appropriate emotional expression is essential for building good interpersonal relationships and social skills, and this is consistent with previous research on the positive correlation between emotional expression and social functioning. Zong (2020) showed that positive emotion regulation strategies are associated with improved psychological well-being and coping skills, and this includes strategies such as seeking social support, exercise and meditation. Students' confident attitudes about their level of emotional control can help foster healthier psychological states and positive social relationships.

The Relationship Between Physical Exercises and Emotional Control in Physical Education

Table 4. Relationship between self-efficacy and autonomous learning abilities

		Emotional Intensity	Emotional Stability	Emotional Expression	Emotion Regulation Strategies	Emotional Control
Frequency	r	.485	.493	.423	.472	.531
	sig	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Decision on Ho Interpretation	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant
Intensity	r	.561	.550	.526	.517	.610
	sig	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Decision on Ho Interpretation	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant
Time	r	.500	.534	.549	.565	.607
	sig	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Decision on Ho Interpretation	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant
Type	r	.466	.480	.617	.625	.616
	sig	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Decision on Ho Interpretation	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant
Physical Exercises	r	.611	.626	.643	.664	.719
	sig	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Decision on Ho Interpretation	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant	Rejected Significant

N=386. Level of Significance: *is noteworthy at the 0.05 level. (2-tailed)

Table 4 demonstrates the relationship between self-efficacy and self-directed learning ability, which includes affective intensity, affective stability, affective expression, affective regulation strategies, and affective control in terms of frequency, intensity, duration, type, and physical exercise.

The r-values in the table indicate the correlations between self-efficacy and each aspect of emotional control. These correlations are all significant as the p-values are less than 0.05, indicating that there is some degree of association between these aspects. The null hypothesis (Ho) for all the relationships was rejected indicating that these correlations are significant. This indicates that there is a

significant relationship between self-efficacy and emotional control in terms of frequency, intensity, duration, type and physical exercise. The significance of the results suggests that individuals are more likely to show better emotional control when they have higher levels of self-efficacy. Specifically, there was a positive relationship between affective intensity, affective stability, affective expression, affective regulation strategies, and overall affective control with self-efficacy.

These results contribute to the understanding of the relationship between self-efficacy and affective control and provide insights to the fields of education and mental health regarding the improvement of students' self-directed learning. In practice, students' self-efficacy can be improved to promote better control of their emotions and thus improve learning.

Zhang et al. (2021) study has already pointed out that an individual's self-efficacy is closely related to his or her ability to regulate emotions. Individuals with high self-efficacy are more likely to use positive emotion regulation strategies, such as seeking social support, exercise, or meditation, to manage emotions more effectively. Wang (2020) showed that the way an individual expresses emotions is related to his or her level of self-efficacy. Individuals with high self-efficacy were more confident in expressing their emotions, whereas low self-efficacy led to internalization of emotions and difficulty in expressing them. Liu (2023) showed that self-efficacy was closely related to an individual's attitudes and behaviors toward participation in physical activity. Individuals with high self-efficacy are more actively involved in physical activity because they believe they can overcome obstacles and succeed. Self-efficacy has been the focus of research in the field of learning. Hou (2020) showed that high self-efficacy was associated with greater academic achievement, more positive attitudes toward learning, and better independent learning.

Taken together, the results in Table 20 further reinforce the importance of self-efficacy in emotional control and self-directed learning and provide useful insights for future research and practice. It also emphasizes the potential benefits of improving individual self-efficacy in education and mental health.

Conclusion

Student respondents were positive in terms of frequency, intensity, duration, and type of physical activity, and overall conformed to the FIT principle, demonstrating a positive commitment to a fitness program. Students excelled in all aspects of affective control (affective intensity, affective stability, affective expression, affective regulation strategies, and overall affective control) and could process and express emotions effectively. There is a significant positive correlation between emotional control and self-efficacy, the better the students perform in emotional control, the higher their self-efficacy. This suggests that improving emotional control can help to increase students' self-efficacy.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Yanwen Lu

Adamson University – Philippines